

THE INFLUENCE OF HERBICIDES ON THE SYNTHESIS OF PHYTOHORMONES BY SOIL MICROORGANISMS

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Annotation. The microorganisms *Pseudomonas putida* R15, *Bacillus cereus* G21, *Bacillus pumilus* R25 and *Streptomyces variabilis* G35 isolated from soil after treatment with herbicides showed the ability to synthesize phytohormones in the cultivation medium: indole-3-acetic (IAA) and gibberellic acids. Different strains showed different synthetic activity. *Bacillus cereus* G21 is the most active producer of extracellular IAA, and *Streptomyces variabilis* R35 of gibberellic acid. The strain *Pseudomonas putida* R15 showed the least activity in the formation of phytohormones.

Key words: soil, microorganisms, phytohormones, herbicides, culture fluid.

Introduction. At present, extensive material has been accumulated on the phytohormonal activity of bacteria and yeast fungi associated with plants and their influence on plant growth, mineral nutrition, and resistance to abiotic stresses [1–3]. The main groups of phytohormones include auxins, gibberellins, cytokinins, abscisic acid, ethylene, salicylic acid, and jasmonates [4].

Rhizobacteria producing IAA can enhance seed germination, increase seedling vigor, and improve plant tolerance to abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and heavy metal toxicity [5–7]. Bacteria belonging to the genera *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* are known as phytohormone producers [8]. The production of IAA by bacteria varies depending on the species and strain, as well as on cultivation conditions, growth stage, and substrate availability [8]. At the same time, IAA-producing rhizobacteria stimulate plant growth in several ways and are considered potential bioinoculants [9]. Previously, we studied the effect of pendimethalin and clethodim on the abundance and diversity of microbial communities and assessed the growth dynamics of strains resistant to these herbicides. In the present study, data are provided on the synthesis of phytohormonal substances (IAA and gibberellin) by these strains.

The aim of the study is to investigate the synthesis of gibberellin and indole-3-acetic acid by bacteria and actinomycetes isolated from soil after the application of herbicides.

Materials and methods. *Pseudomonas putida* R15, *Bacillus cereus* G21, *Bacillus pumilus* R25, and *Streptomyces variabilis* G35 were cultured on a synthetic medium, while the actinomycete was grown in liquid Gauze nutrient medium on a rotary shaker (Shaker-Incubator

ES-20/80, Biosan) at 150 rpm, with a cell titer of 10^6 cells/ml. Cultivation was carried out at 28 °C for 7 days. The concentration of IAA produced by the strains *Pseudomonas putida* R15, *Bacillus cereus* G21, *Bacillus pumilus* G25, and *Streptomyces variabilis* R35 was determined on a photoelectric colorimeter (PEC) according to the method of Glickmann and Dessaux [10]. A calibration curve for IAA determination was constructed based on the hormone content in the test solution. Then, 1 ml of the studied solution was vigorously mixed with 4 ml of Salkowski reagent (150 ml concentrated H_2SO_4 , 250 ml distilled H_2O , 7.5 ml 0.5 M $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$) and left to stand for 20 min at room temperature before spectrophotometric measurement. Absorbance was determined at a wavelength of 530 nm using a red light filter in 10 mm cuvettes. The IAA concentration in each sample (variant) was determined by comparison with the standard calibration curve.

Results and discussion. The study examined the ability of microorganisms to synthesize phytohormones, gibberellin, and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) during growth dynamics. The obtained results show that the soil-isolated strains exhibit different capacities for IAA synthesis. Thus, the maximum amount of IAA was obtained in the culture liquid of *Bacillus cereus* G21, reaching 232 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on day 3 (136 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on day 2). The accumulation of IAA by the strain *Bacillus pumilus* G25 amounted to 102 and 116 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on days 2 and 3, respectively. The strain *Pseudomonas putida* R15 showed lower synthesizing ability, with IAA content in the solution reaching 68 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on day 3 and 77 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on day 4 (Fig. 1). As can be seen from the presented data, the studied bacterial strains produced the maximum amount of IAA on days 3 and 4, while a decrease in IAA content was observed in the 5-day culture liquid.

Fig. 1. Formation of IAA by bacteria during growth dynamics

The effect of IAA production by the streptomycete strain *Streptomyces variabilis* G35 was evaluated over 7 days, with its maximum content observed on the 5th day of incubation, amounting to 246 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. By the 7th day, a decrease in indole-3-acetic acid content to 154 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was noted (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. IAA content in the culture liquid of the studied strain *Streptomyces variabilis* G35

Similar results were obtained by Harikrishnan H. et al. [10], who isolated the strain *Streptomyces* sp. VSMGT1014 from soil at an optimal temperature of 30°C. Under these conditions, maximum IAA biosynthesis was observed on the 5th day of incubation; among the seven tested media, the highest IAA production was recorded in ISP2 medium (9.26 µg/ml).

The studied strains also showed activity in gibberellin synthesis. Thus, it was found that the gibberellin content in the culture liquid of *Streptomyces variabilis* G35 was the highest, reaching 425 µg/ml on the 5th day. In terms of gibberellin synthesis activity, bacterial strains demonstrated lower activity compared to the actinomycete, ranking in the following order: the highest activity was shown by *Bacillus cereus* G21 – 256 µg/ml on the 4th day, *Bacillus pumilus* G25 – 186.0 µg/ml on the 3rd day, and the lowest activity was observed in *Pseudomonas putida* R15, in whose culture liquid 82 µg/ml was detected on the 3rd day (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Gibberellin formation by microorganisms during growth dynamics

Conclusion. Thus, the obtained data show that all the studied bacteria – *Bacillus cereus* G21, *Bacillus pumilus* R25, *Pseudomonas putida* R15 – and the actinomycete *Streptomyces*

variabilis G35, isolated from soil after herbicide treatment, produce gibberellin and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA). The maximum content of gibberellin and IAA in bacteria was observed on the 3rd–4th days of culture growth, while in the actinomycete it was observed on the 5th day. Depending on the strain, the maximum gibberellin content ranged from 82.0 to 425 µg/ml, and IAA content ranged from 54 to 246 µg/ml.

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